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User-centric and data-driven retrofitting solutions for a resilient, energy-efficient, low-emission and inclusive cultural heritage.

D5.1 Herit4ages Energy Router and NILM

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Summary

This deliverable reports the outcomes of Task 5.2. It presents the sizing, simulation, and laboratory tests of the power electronics Smart Energy Router in order to manage the energy flow in the building, the Battery system in order to enhance the use of energy flexibility, the solar photovoltaic collectors to be integrated without compromising the cultural identity of the building, and the non-intrusive load monitoring methodology in order to allow the load detection and facilitate energy management schemes.

Different scenarios were defined in order to validate the correct operation of both systems.

Regarding the Smart Energy Router, a comprehensive simulation study was performed using dedicated simulation software to validate the calculated values, the main functionalities, control algorithms, and modulation methods. The simulation results show a correct operation of the device in the different scenarios. Furthermore, the different scenarios were also tested in laboratory at UNINOVA facilities, with similar results.

As far as the NILM is considered, this deliverable presents the adopted algorithms and the laboratory experiments of those algorithms.

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Terms, definitions, and abbreviated terms

CMF	Camara Municipal do Funchal
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
ESS	Energy Storage System
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FSMLR	Fundacion Santa Maria la Real del Patrimonio Historico
GA	Genetic Algorithms
IDP	Ingenieria Y Arquitectura Iberia
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
MPP	Maximum Power Point
MOV	Metal Oxide Varistor
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
NILM	Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring
OC	Over-Current
OV	Over-Voltage
P&O	Perturb and Observe
PEBB	Power Electronics Building Blocks
PV	Photovoltaic
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
RMS	Root Mean Square
RPPT	Reverse Power Point Tracking
SER	Smart Energy Router
SoC	State of Charge
TYN	University College Cork
UNI	UNINOVA

Executive summary

This document details the design, simulation, and testing of the Smart Energy Router and the non-intrusive load monitoring methodology for energy-efficient retrofitting of cultural heritage buildings.

The Smart Energy Router (SER) manages the energy flow, integrating solar photovoltaic (PV), Battery storage, and the home grid. Two sets of PVs were considered: one standard PV and one aesthetic PV panel to be integrated without compromising the cultural identity of the building. The design was validated through simulations, using SCAD/EMTDCi software, and laboratory tests under distinct operating scenarios. Results demonstrate accurate control and power management across different operating conditions.

A novel high-frequency Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) methodology was developed. It uses Fast Fourier Transforms to extract individual appliance signatures from aggregate current data, and Genetic Algorithms to identify simultaneous appliance operation. Laboratory tests with six appliances show accurate disaggregation procedure.

The deliverable presents specifications, sizing calculations, control algorithms, simulation results, and laboratory test results for both the Smart Energy Router and the Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring system, demonstrating successful development and initial validation.

1. Planned Criteria

This deliverable (D5.1) describes the Herit4ages SER and NILM specifications along with the initial set of laboratory results, developed under the scope of WP5 (Energy sustainable integration solutions) of the Herit4Ages project. The SER and the NILM algorithm will be implemented as energy improvement measures in the Heritage Living Lab of Funchal, as described in deliverable D2.4 (Heritage living labs context and requirements report and KPIs), contributing to achieve the respective KPIs, also described in deliverable D2.4.

WP5 aims to develop a power electronics energy router to optimize the energy flow among the building, local renewable sources, energy storage systems, and the grid; along with the design of an innovative biodegradable sensor utilizing direct laser writing on biopolymer substrates. This will enhance the sustainability of demonstration sites while providing a cost-effective boost to overall energy performance and improving user comfort. The use of non-intrusive load monitoring, to identify the operation of devices and equipment without needing intrusive assessments on the pilot sites, will support implementing energy flexibility and demand-side strategies to increase energy efficiency. WP5 extends from M6 to M48 and involved partners are UNI (Leader), FSM, IDP, CMF and TYN.

D5.1 (Herit4ages Energy Router and NILM) describes the necessary steps to develop and deploy the respective prototypes, and has been developed under the context of Task T5.1 – “Technologies and sustainable integration specifications”. This task oversees defining the specifications of the developed technologies and components involved in the efficient energy usage. These technologies include aesthetic solar PV collectors to be integrated without compromising the cultural identity of the building, power electronics Smart Energy Router to manage the energy flow in the building, Battery system in order to enhance the use of energy flexibility, and NILM in order to allow the non-intrusive load detection and facilitate energy saving schemes.

2. Smart Energy Router overview

The Smart Energy Router is a multi-directional power electronic interface with the following ports: AC port for home grid connection, DC port for energy storage, and a 2xDC port for PV panel connection (standard and aesthetic photovoltaic panel types). It manages the energy transfer from renewable sources, loads and energy storage system. The Smart Energy Router is established according to the IEEE Power Electronics Building Blocks (PEBB) concept, where basic

building blocks are consistent with one another, have a defined functionality, standardized hardware and control interfaces, making it easier to be adapted and scalable to different scenarios. The Smart Energy Router executes intelligent algorithms that assure the fulfilment of operation rules and choose the best available operating option, providing energy flow control and smart energy management.

The block diagram of the proposed Smart Energy Router is presented in Figure 1. Such a system allows the control of several power flow situations, and it is composed of the following power stages and sub-systems:

- PV generation system (standard and aesthetic PV panels);
- DC-DC converters as interface between the PV arrays and the common DC-link;
- Bidirectional DC-DC converter for Battery storage system charging and discharging;
- DC-AC converter connecting to the home electrical system.

FIGURE 1 STRUCTURE OF THE SMART ENERGY ROUTER

The selected power topology circuits are presented in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2 POWER TOPOLOGY FOR THE SMART ENERGY ROUTER

An isolated full bridge DC-DC converter was selected for the PV DC-DC converters, composed of a high-frequency power transformer (T_1), 4 switches (S_1 to S_4), and a rectifier bridge (D_1 to D_4). The PV panels are directly connected to the DC-DC converter, while C_{DC} form the common DC-link for the full system. Its main functionality is the maximum power extraction from both PV arrays (MPPT – Maximum Power Point Tracking operation) or the provision of any feasible reference value of power (RPPT Reserve Power Point Tracking operation). They are depicted in Figure 2 as the two subsystems highlighted in green.

An isolated dual active bridge converter was selected for the Battery DC-DC converter, composed of a high-frequency power transformer (T_3) and 8 switches (S_{13} to S_{20}). The Battery is directly connected to the DC-DC converter, while C_{DC} forms the common DC-link for the whole system. Its main functionality will be charging and discharging the Battery allowing for demanding or injecting power from/to the common DC link bus. It is depicted in Figure 2 as the subsystem highlighted in light orange.

A single-phase full-bridge DC-AC bidirectional power converter is in charge of interfacing the energy generation system with the home electrical system. Composed of 4 switches (S_9, \dots, S_{12}) and LC filter (L_f and C_f), this DC-AC converter will be responsible for the main functionalities and services concerning self-consumption optimization. It is depicted in Figure 2 as the sub-system highlighted in blue.

Input capacitors, C_{PV1} , C_{PV2} and C_{EES} , smooth the input voltage by filtering out eventual ripple effect. Electrical isolation is assured by using high-frequency power transformers in the DC-DC converters. The DC-link common bus is stabilized by the capacitor bank represented by C_{DC} . DC-link voltage will be controlled by the grid interface.

3. Smart Energy Router sizing

This section presents the sizing of the different SER interfaces: PV strings, Energy Storage System (ESS) composed by the Battery system, and output inverter for home grid connection.

3.1.1 Home grid interface sizing

In a single-phase full-bridge DC-AC converter is necessary to calculate and estimate the output filter (C_f and L_f components, shown in Figure 2). This component is essential for Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) converters. Some technical documents cover the output filter design [2][3][4][5][6]. L, LC, LCL and LLCL output filters are commonly used in this kind of power converter. However, an LC filter was selected to mitigate the high frequency harmonics, measure the capacitor voltage and control it during the island operation. There are several criteria that can be considered for L selection. For instance, the ripple criteria ensures that the error between the converter's reference current and the grid-injected current remains within a margin regulated by the power quality standards (usually between 5% and 15%). The criteria used is based on the current ripple calculation on the switching harmonic. Figure 3 shows a typical harmonic spectrum of the DC-AC converter. It is possible to define the converter voltage harmonic at the switching frequency.

FIGURE 3 HARMONIC SPECTRUM

Assuming that the switching frequency directly and exclusively influences the current ripple, Equation 1 is considered, where I_{sw} is the grid RMS harmonic current at the switching frequency, I_1 is the RMS value of the current fundamental harmonic.

$$THD_I \approx \sqrt{\frac{I_{sw}^2}{I_1^2}} = \frac{I_{sw}}{I_1} \quad (1)$$

The inductor (L_f) plays a pivotal role in the output filter, as it is responsible for filtering out the harmonics of the switching frequency. The inductor's design is contingent on the calculation of the current ripple and the selection of a material for the core that can withstand the calculated current ripple.

The voltage across the inductor is given by Equation 2.

$$V_L = L \frac{di}{dt} \quad (2)$$

The full-bridge inverter with an AC output can be expressed as follows:

$$V_{DC-LINK} - V_{home} = L \frac{\Delta i_{pp}}{D \times \left(\frac{1}{f_{sw}}\right)} \quad (3)$$

The inductance value that is required in order to tolerate the ripple is given by Equation 4.

$$L_f = \frac{V_{DC-LINK}}{4 \times f_{sw} \times \Delta i_{pp}} \quad (4)$$

As the voltage harmonic component at the switching frequency is unknown, the current ripple can be estimated directly from this calculation using the converter voltage waveform. Typically, such an approach gives the same result, since there is a proportional relation between the two magnitudes: ripple and content of harmonics. It is assumed that the ripple is 20% and is tolerable by the inductor core.

The output inductor and capacitor form a low-pass filter that filters out the switching frequency. Achieving optimal switching frequency attenuation requires maintaining the cut-off frequency at $f_{sw}/10$ or lower. The filter capacitor (C_f) is added in parallel to the single-phase home grid and

calculated using Equation 5. The cut-off frequency (f_c) is considered 3000 Hz, in order to mitigate the high switching components of the output current.

$$f_c = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot \sqrt{L_f \cdot C_f}} \quad (5)$$

Choosing the right switching frequency for a single-phase inverter is crucial for balancing efficiency, size, and electromagnetic interference (EMI). Additionally, selecting the appropriate DC link voltage is essential to ensure proper operation and avoid excessive current stresses. Table 1 presents the specification for the DC-link voltage as well as the switching frequency.

TABLE 1 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE DC-LINK AND SWITCHING FREQUENCY

Parameter	Value
RMS home grid phase to neutral voltage (V_{home})	230 V
Considered DC-link voltage (V_{DC})	500 V
Considered switching frequency (f_{sw})	30 kHz
Fundamental frequency (f_{grid})	50 Hz

Table 2 presents the specification, rated values and calculated values for the output filter.

TABLE 2 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE OUTPUT FILTER

Parameter	Value
SER Rated Power (P_{ER})	5 kW
RMS home grid phase to neutral voltage (V_{home})	230 V
Fundamental frequency (f_{home})	50 Hz
THD _i	5 %
Minimum SER output inductance filter (L_f)	677 μ H
Minimum SER output capacitance filter (C_f)	4.16 μ F

3.1.2 DC-link capacitor selection

Sizing the DC-link bus capacitor is critical to ensure bus voltage stability. There are two main sources of ripple on the DC-link bus:

- 100 Hz ripple due to the inverter

The single-phase inverter consumes pulsating power at 100 Hz, causing current fluctuations in the DC bus. To attenuate this ripple, the minimum capacitance is given by Equation 6.

$$C_{DC} = \frac{P_{ER}}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot f_{grid} \cdot V_{DC} \cdot \Delta V_{DC}} \quad (6)$$

- High-frequency ripple due to the inverter and the DC-DC converter

The switching of the inverter and the DC-DC converter generates additional oscillations. High-frequency ripple is reduced by a low ESR capacitor (polymer or film). The typical value is given by Equation 7.

$$C_{DC_hf} = \frac{I_{out_rms}}{8 \cdot f_{sw} \cdot \Delta V_{DC}} \quad (7)$$

The specifications of this passive component are summarized in Table 3.

TABLE 3 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE DC-LINK

Parameter	Value
SER Rated Power (P_{ER})	5 kW
DC-link voltage (V_{DC})	500 V
Fundamental frequency (f_{grid})	50 Hz
Switching frequency (f_{sw})	30 kHz
Allowable voltage ripple on the DC-link bus (ΔV_{DC})	25 V (5 %)
Minimum DC-link capacitor value (C_{DC})	1.3 mF
Minimum high-frequency DC-link capacitor value (C_{DC_hf})	3.6 μ F

3.1.3 PV interfaces sizing

For the interface with the PV system, a Full-Bridge DC-DC converter is considered, which consists of a full-bridge circuit on the input side, a high-frequency transformer and a rectifier bridge at the output, making it a unidirectional converter.

The following four parameters need to be calculated to size the power circuit that composes the DC-DC PV converter:

- PV input voltage range: minimum PV input voltage ($V_{PV,m}$) and maximum PV input voltage ($V_{PV,M}$);
- Maximum PV output current ($I_{PV,M}$);
- High-frequency power transformer ratio;
- Integrated circuit, discrete semiconductor or power module to build the converter.

The standard PV array (PV1) was considered as input voltage 70 V at the Maximum Power Point (MPP), and as nominal power 4000 W at standard irradiance and temperature conditions. The converter uses a high-frequency transformer to isolate and adapt voltage levels. The turns ratio n is given by Equation 8.

$$n = \frac{V_{pri}}{V_{sec}} = \frac{V_{in}}{V_{out}} \quad (8)$$

The minimum capacitance for the input capacitor can be approximated by Equation 9, where ΔV is the ripple tolerance in the voltage.

$$C \geq \frac{I_{in}}{8 \cdot f_{sw} \cdot \Delta V} \quad (9)$$

Table 4 shows the specified values for the interface PV1 (string 1).

TABLE 4 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE STANDARD PV PANEL INTERFACE.

Parameter	Value
Maximum power point voltage (V_{MPP})	360 V
Minimum PV input voltage ($V_{PV,m}$)	100 V
Maximum PV input voltage ($V_{PV,M}$)	500 V
Nominal DC-link voltage (V_{DC_link})	500 V
Maximum power point (MPP)	4000 W
Maximum PV output current ($I_{PV,M}$)	13 A
Power transformer ratio (n)	0.72
Input capacitance (C_{in})	3 μ F

For the aesthetic PV array (PV2), it was considered as input voltage 40 V at the Maximum Power Point (MPP) and as nominal power 1031 W at standard irradiance and temperature conditions. The obtained values are presented in Table 5.

TABLE 5 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE AESTHETIC PV PANEL INTERFACE

Parameter	Value
Maximum power point voltage (V_{MPP})	40 V
Minimum PV input voltage ($V_{PV,m}$)	16 V
Maximum PV input voltage ($V_{PV,M}$)	60 V
Nominal DC-link voltage (V_{DC_link})	500 V
Maximum power point (MPP)	1031 W
Maximum PV output current ($I_{PV,M}$)	26 A
Power transformer ratio (n)	0.08
Input capacitance (C_{in})	54.2 μ F ($\Delta V = 5\%$)

3.1.4 Battery systems interface sizing

A Dual Active Bridge (DAB) is a bidirectional DC-DC converter comprising identical full-bridge circuits on both the primary and secondary sides, a high-frequency transformer, an energy transfer inductor, and DC-link capacitors. The energy transfer inductance represents the transformer's leakage inductance combined with any additional external inductance required for efficient power transfer. The following four parameters need to be calculated to size the power circuit that composes the DC-DC Battery converter:

- Battery input voltage range: minimum Battery input voltage ($V_{\text{Bat,m}}$) and maximum Battery input voltage ($V_{\text{Bat,M}}$);
- Maximum Battery output current ($I_{\text{Bat,M}}$);
- High-frequency power transformer ratio;
- Integrated circuit, discrete semiconductor or power module to build the converter.

The converter uses a high frequency transformer to isolate and adapt voltage levels. The turns ratio n is given by Equation 10.

$$n = \frac{V_{pri}}{V_{sec}} = \frac{V_{in}}{V_{out}} \quad (10)$$

The minimum capacitance for the input capacitor can be approximated by Equation 11, where ΔV is the ripple tolerance in the voltage.

$$C \geq \frac{I_{in}}{8 \cdot f_{sw} \cdot \Delta V} \quad (11)$$

Table 6 shows the specified values for the Battery interface.

TABLE 6 SPECIFICATIONS OF THE BATTERY INTERFACE.

Parameter	Value
Minimum Battery input voltage ($V_{Bat,m}$)	48 V
Maximum Battery input voltage ($V_{Bat,M}$)	500 V
Nominal DC-link voltage (V_{DC_link})	500 V
Nominal Battery power (P_{Bat})	3 kW
Maximum Battery output current ($I_{Bat,M}$)	62.5 A
Power transformer ratio (n)	0.096
Input capacitance (C_{in})	109 μ F ($\Delta V = 5\%$)

3.1.5 Protection Scheme

The Smart Energy Router is protected based on MOV varistors. The AC input (phase and neutral) is protected with fuses which will blow in both over-current (OC) and over-voltage (OV) fault events. For the OV fault event, the fuse will blow only when the input voltage exceeds the clamp voltage of the varistor directly connected to the phase.

3.2 Smart Energy Router control algorithms

A two-level control system is considered in order to optimally operate the Smart Energy Router (converter and supervision levels), as presented in Figure 4.

The Converter Level Control System includes the necessary input/output channels (such as digital and analogue channels and PWM output channels) to control the Smart Energy Router components (power converters), as well as the implementation of the control algorithms of each component. Converter-level control commands are, for example, converter turn on/ turn off, power set-points for each connected device or operation mode.

The Supervision Level Control aims to manage the Smart Energy Router high-level strategy receiving the operation modes (MPPT or RPPT PV modes, storage charging and/or discharging) and to manage the energy flow between the different connected devices (PV, storage device,

grid). This supervision level also monitors the Smart Energy Router's functioning and handles error codes, deciding the necessary steps to eliminate or mitigate them.

The communication between both control levels is conducted by means of serial communication.

FIGURE 4 SMART ENERGY ROUTER CONTROL SCHEME

The general block diagram of the control structure is presented in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5 BLOCK DIAGRAM OF THE SMART ENERGY ROUTER CONTROL STRATEGY

The DC-AC converter operates with a direct (d) component reference current ($i_{d,ref}$) obtained by a DC-link control loop. This control loop forces the system to maintain a constant voltage of

the DC-link at the desired level. The current tracking control is based on the predictive control type with a dead-beat current controller. The power exchange between Battery and DC-link is controlled using the external control block according to the Battery state of charge (SoC) and user specifications. The DC-DC PV converters will extract the maximum power from the PV array or any feasible active power reference. The MPPT is based on the Perturb and Observe algorithm.

3.3 Operating scenarios

Multiple scenarios were established to verify the proper functioning of the smart Energy Router. They are divided as follows:

- A) PV system operates at MPPT mode, Battery discharges and charges, and DC-AC SER inverter injects power into the home grid.
- B) PV system is operating at RPPT mode, Battery discharges and charges, and DC-AC SER inverter injects power into the home grid.
- C) PV system is OFF, Battery discharges and charges, and DC-AC SER converter injects power into the home grid.

3.4 Simulation results

To validate the calculated parameters, along with the key functionalities, control algorithms, and modulation methods, a thorough simulation study was conducted using PSCAD/EMTDCi software [1]. This section provides all the details and analysed scenarios. It is crucial to highlight that the necessary measurements were sampled to align with the control frequency rate used in the SER controller, enhancing the realism of the simulation for real-world implementation.

3.4.1 Scenario A

Scenario A aims to validate the working conditions when the PV system is operating in MPPT mode. Figure 6 shows the evolution of the reference MPP voltage, whose magnitude is obtained by using the MPPT algorithm based on Perturb and Observe (P&O) with adaptive step [2][3]. The PV voltage and the PV current track the reference and nominal values with accuracy in the steady state respectively. Figure 7 illustrates the PV current in a steady state, once the MPPT has been achieved. The PV current ripple indicates that this value remains within the design limits.

FIGURE 6 SCENARIO A: PV VOLTAGE , MPP REFERENCE VOLTAGE AND PV CURRENT.

FIGURE 7 SCENARIO A: PV CURRENT RIPPLE.

The ESS, which is composed by the Battery associated with the SER, charging and discharging procedure is presented in Figure 8. The Battery is first discharged and then charged with a reference power of 75% of the nominal Battery power. The Battery SoC decreases and increases accordingly. The Battery current and the Battery voltage are also depicted, and the Battery current ripple is under the sizing specifications. The PV power and Battery power are injected

into the home grid using the DC-AC SER inverter, where sinusoidal currents are obtained and injected (presented in Figure 9). Figure 9 presents the AC home grid voltage and injected current, the PV current and the Battery current. In this simulation both, PV and Battery, are providing power to supply the home grid.

FIGURE 8 SCENARIO A: SER VOLTAGE AND SER CURRENT DURING ESS DISCHARGE AND CHARGING STAGES.

FIGURE 9 SCENARIO A: SER VOLTAGE, SER CURRENT, ESS CURRENT, AND PV CURRENT.

The primary DC-link voltage is also shown in Figure 10, and its value is kept at the nominal level defined by the DC-link reference value (as outlined in Table 3), exhibiting the effective operation of the DC-link control loop.

FIGURE 10 SCENARIO A: EVOLUTION OF THE MAIN DC-LINK VOLTAGE DURING SER START-UP.

3.4.2 Scenario B

Scenario B is similar to scenario A but considering that the full PV power cannot be used. In this case the SER controller changes from MPPT operation mode to RPPT operation mode, where the PV power is controlled according to a specified set point level. In this simulation, scenario B considers the PV system operating with a reference equal to 75% of the PV panel nominal value (RPPT mode). In this simulation, only one PV panel was considered, and the same reference power values were given to the ESS converter as in scenario A. The PV DC-DC converter provides a similar response to that in scenario A. Figure 11 depicts the evolution of reference power point. The PV voltage and current track the desired values with accuracy in the steady state.

FIGURE 11 SCENARIO B: PV VOLTAGE, RPP REFERENCE VOLTAGE, AND PV CURRENT.

The magnitudes analysis of the DC-DC Battery converter is also presented in Figure 12. The Battery is discharged and then charged with the same reference power as in scenario A. The Battery SoC decreases and increases accordingly. The Battery current and the Battery voltage are also depicted.

FIGURE 12 SCENARIO B: SER VOLTAGE AND SER CURRENT DURING ESS DISCHARGE AND CHARGING STAGES.

3.4.3 Scenario C

Scenario C illustrates the capability of the Smart Energy Router to supply home loads when the PV system is unavailable (e.g., at night). In this scenario, the Battery can be charged and discharged without relying on PV power. As shown in Figure 13, the Battery SoC decreases (while supplying the home loads) and increases (being supplied by the Distribution System Operator’s grid). The slope rates are also higher since a higher power reference was considered for this simulation. The Battery SoC decreases and increases accordingly. The Battery current and the Battery voltage are also depicted.

FIGURE 13 SCENARIO C: SER VOLTAGE AND SER CURRENT DURING ESS DISCHARGE AND CHARGING STAGES.

3.5 Laboratory tests

The assembled system, built according to the specified requirements and sizing, was tested under various scenarios to confirm its proper performance. Figure 14 presents a partial inner view of the SER prototype.

FIGURE 14 SMART ENERGY ROUTER PROTOTYPE INNER VIEW

3.5.1 Scenario A

The first test is designed to verify the proper operation of the initial prototype regarding the active power balance between the PV system, Battery, and home grid. The primary waveforms are illustrated in Figure 15, with the home grid voltage in yellow, the SER injected current in cyan, the PV current in green, and the Battery current in purple. The PV current demonstrates effective tracking of maximum power with a current ripple that remains within acceptable limits. The shown Battery current reflects a discharging process, with the combined power from the PV and Battery being injected into the home grid.

FIGURE 15 SCENARIO A (BATTERY DISCHARGING): SER VOLTAGE, SER CURRENT, ESS CURRENT, AND PV CURRENT.

Figure 16 displays the same tests, but with a reference for charging the Battery. Since the MPPT is higher than the charging reference, the Smart Energy Router continues to inject power into the home grid.

FIGURE 16 SCENARIO A (BATTERY CHARGING): SER VOLTAGE, SER CURRENT, ESS CURRENT, AND PV CURRENT.

3.5.2 Scenario B

In this scenario, the PV system operates in RPPT mode. Figure 17 illustrates a use case in which both the PV and Battery references contribute to an additive power injection into the home grid. The primary waveforms are shown, with home grid voltage in yellow, SER injected current in cyan, PV current in green, and Battery current in purple. The PV current demonstrates effective tracking of its reference. The positive Battery current indicates a discharging mode, with the resulting power being injected into the home grid.

FIGURE 17 SCENARIO B (BATTERY DISCHARGING): SER VOLTAGE, SER CURRENT, ESS CURRENT, AND PV CURRENT.

The same test but with a charging ESS reference is presented in Figure 18. The RPPT is higher than the ESS charging reference, so the SER is still injecting power into the home grid.

FIGURE 18 SCENARIO B (BATTERY CHARGING): SER VOLTAGE, SER CURRENT, ESS CURRENT, AND PV CURRENT.

3.5.3 Scenario C

This scenario experimentally showcases the performance of the Smart Energy Router when the PV system is turned off (e.g., at night). In this case, the PV current is zero, and the Battery discharges power to supply the home grid, as illustrated in Figure 19.

FIGURE 19 SCENARIO C: SER VOLTAGE, SER CURRENT, ESS CURRENT, AND PV CURRENT.

4. Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM)

The most accurate way to extract the consumption pattern of appliances is intrusive load monitoring, although this is an unpractical approach, particularly in heritage buildings. Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring was first established in 1992 [7] and is a methodology that analyses the total electricity consumption of a household and separates it into individual appliance usage without installing extra sensors on every appliance.

4.1 Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) overview

Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring (NILM) is a methodology used to establish energy consumption patterns of individual appliances within a building without needing individual sub-meters. NILM analyses the aggregate electrical signal entering a building to identify the distinct electrical signatures of different devices. This information allows users to gain insights about their energy usage, identify which appliances are consume the most energy, the time they are connected, and make informed decisions to improve energy efficiency. NILM is often used in smart home

systems and energy management applications. Having many different approaches, a good review of NILM techniques can be found in the work conducted by Habetler et al. [8].

4.2 Low-frequency methods

NILM algorithms using low-frequency data, focus on macroscopic characteristics like active and reactive power variations, or state change probability of some appliances based on consumer usage patterns. Several methods were developed, each with varying effectiveness. The first Hart's algorithm uses simple signature matching but struggles with similar-consumption appliances [7]. Baranski's method employs genetic algorithms and HMMs, improving accuracy but requiring more computational resources [9]. Other approaches consider not only active power changes, but also reactive and distortion power [10]. While simpler methods may be computationally efficient, they often sacrifice accuracy. More complex approaches, while more accurate, demand significant computational resources and training data. One example is the Parson's algorithm, which uses hidden Markov models.[11]

4.3 High-frequency methods

NILM's high-frequency methods uses high-frequency data acquisition, focusing on microscopic characteristics like harmonic analysis of current signals. Transient-based methods, such as the one described by Shaw et al. [12], leverage the unique spectral signatures of appliances during power-on/off events. However, these require pre-training and may struggle with similar signatures. Steady-state methods, like the one by Srinivasan et al. [13], use harmonic content during normal operation, but are computationally intensive and require extensive training data, often resulting in limited scalability and real-time applicability. Methods based on time-frequency analysis yield good results but are computationally demanding [14]. Ultimately, the choice of method depends on a balance between computational cost and desired accuracy.

4.4 NILM methodology development

Most NILM methods struggle to disaggregate multiple simultaneously operating devices. While some methods exist, they are usually computationally complex and demanding.

This project will employ a novel disaggregation method based on the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the current signal and Genetic Algorithms (GAs). Each device is characterized by its unique electrical signature, extracted via FFT from the global current waveform. Device disaggregation is achieved through the optimized solution generated by the Genetic Algorithm.

Each gene in the solution represents a specific electrical device; a gene value of one indicates the device's inclusion in the solution. Therefore, each gene symbolizes an individual device, and each chromosome (gene sequence) encodes a unique set of devices, preventing duplicate aggregations. Using a binary chromosome, the developed methodology can identify 2^n-1 possible aggregations, where n is the number of genes. With 3 genes (each representing an appliance), up to 7 distinct aggregations can be encoded. Each chromosome uniquely characterizes an event, representing the simultaneous activation of one or more devices.

4.5 Laboratory tests

To test the feasibility and accuracy of the developed algorithm several laboratory tests were conducted considering six distinct appliances: hair dryer (inductive load; 1600W); microwave (non-linear load; 800W); toaster (resistive load; 700W); power tool (non-linear load; 620W); magic wand (non linear load; 200W) and electric boiler (resistive load; 1500W). The following figures present the current signal, and the Fourier Transform for each of the considered appliances.

FIGURE 20 HAIR DRYER CURRENT SIGNAL AND FOURIER TRANSFORM.

FIGURE 21 MICROWAVE CURRENT SIGNAL AND FOURIER TRANSFORM.

FIGURE 22 TOASTER CURRENT SIGNAL AND FOURIER TRANSFORM.

FIGURE 23 POWER TOOL CURRENT SIGNAL AND FOURIER TRANSFORM.

FIGURE 24 MAGIC WAND CURRENT SIGNAL AND FOURIER TRANSFORM.

FIGURE 25 ELECTRIC BOILER CURRENT SIGNAL AND FOURIER TRANSFORM.

Several tests were conducted (for single and simultaneous switching on of the six appliances), as presented in Table 7, and the developed algorithm accurately detected all the considered appliances.

TABLE 7 NILM TESTS PERFORMED ON THE LABORATORY

Electric Boiler	Microwave	Magic Wand	Power Tool	Hair Dryer	Toaster
				X	X
	X			X	
X					X
		X		X	X
			X	X	
	X			X	X
	X			X	
X				X	X

5. Conclusions

A comprehensive simulation study was performed in the PSCAD/EMTDCi software to validate the sizing values, main functionalities, control algorithms, and modulation methods for the Smart Energy Router prototype. Different scenarios were defined in order to validate the correct operation of the SER, namely: A – PV system is operating at MPPT mode; B – PV system is operating at RPPT mode, and C – PV system is OFF. The scenarios were analyzed and simulated, showing correct operation of the SER in all the different scenarios. The SER prototype was primarily tested in laboratory and initially validated.

A high-frequency NILM methodology was developed, employing FFT for device identification and GA for identifying events involving simultaneous device activation. Laboratory testing yielded accurate results.

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